

ECONOMY

SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL PRACTICE IN UTTAR PRADESH: A COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF EXPENDITURES INCURRED BY FARMERS IN ACQUIRING HIGH ENERGY INPUTS AND THE TOTAL RETURN ON WHEAT CULTIVATION IN A SEASON.

Bibhu Prasad Sahoo

Dr.

S.G.T.B. Khalsa College

University of Delhi

Abstract

This study examines the sustainability of agricultural practices in Uttar Pradesh by conducting a cost-benefit analysis of the expenditures incurred by farmers in acquiring high-energy inputs and the total return on wheat cultivation over a season. The research focuses on quantifying the financial implications of adopting modern, energy-intensive farming techniques compared to traditional methods. By analyzing data from a representative sample of wheat farmers, the study evaluates input costs, including seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, and irrigation, against the yield and market value of the wheat produced. The findings reveal a complex interplay between initial investment and return on investment, highlighting the economic viability and potential financial risks associated with high-energy agricultural inputs. Additionally, the study explores the environmental and socio-economic impacts of these practices, providing a comprehensive overview of their sustainability. The results offer valuable insights for policymakers, agricultural planners, and farmers, suggesting pathways to optimize resource use while ensuring economic and environmental sustainability in wheat cultivation in Uttar Pradesh. The study found that new generation farmers prefer more powerful tractors and older farmers use more conventional tillage methods. Educated farmers are more likely to adopt new methods and machines to reduce fuel use in farm operations.

Keywords: Energy, Co2 emissions, sustainable practices, agricultural practice, inputs.

Introduction:

The green revolution of the 1960s in India was a significant technological breakthrough aimed at combating malnutrition in developing countries. It involved the use of high-yielding seeds, chemical fertilizers, and heavy irrigation to increase crop yields. However, this success was unevenly distributed among different farm sizes and across states, leading to a significant disparity between the rich and poor. For centuries, farmers in India used organic farming methods, such as crop rotation and natural forests, which maintained soil fertility and stability. However, the Green Revolution led to the adoption of mono-cropping, a modern method of cropping that cultivated only one crop rather than multiple. This method negatively affected soil fertility and required higher inputs of chemical fertilizers and plant nutrients. The high-yielding seeds had a narrow genetic base, leading to the displacement of indigenous species and agricultural systems built over generations. Trees that protected fields were cut, leaving soil vulnerable to erosion and plants exposed to harsh weather. Hence, the green revolution in India has led to a significant shift in agriculture, resulting in a disparity between the rich and poor.

The world's demand for petroleum and natural gas is increasing, ahead of its supplies. This demand is expected to continue rising as the population grows and improves their quality of life. Higher prices of petrol, diesel, and natural gas can be expected in the future unless renewable energy sources are replaced. Energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions are increasing at unprecedented rates, posing a threat to global health and environmental stability. The Kyoto Protocol has confirmed that GHGs should be reduced to below 1990 levels by 2012. With an increasing world population and living standards, the demand for energy is expected to rise even further. Technology addresses the

efficient utilization of these four ingredients of physical changes, and conscious energy conservation is crucial.

The oil price shock in the 1970s and 1980s led to increased interest in new technologies and strategies to create more efficient systems in various sectors, such as industry, transport, and agriculture. Agricultural engineers have been concerned with the efficiency of energy application in the sector, which is essential for improving energy systems. Energy consumption in agricultural production depends on several parameters, including machine and human factors, direct and indirect factors, and uncontrolled variables. Conventional data-processing methods are not suitable for investigating process and product parameters due to their stochastic nature and dependence on many parameters. In India, improving the energy efficiency of Indian agriculture is a critical issue for the world from both a climate change and energy security perspective. However, the picture is made immensely complex due to the entrenched policy of providing "free power" to farmers since the Green Revolution of the 1970s.

What is Sustainable agriculture?

Sustainable agriculture is often defined and confined conventional farming and creates confusion. In fact, it helps to improve and restore soil health by integrating all possible measures so that crop productivity is maintained for a longer time. According to United Nations Development Programme, sustainable development means national food security, upgrading living standard of farmers, and conservation of the natural resources. Thus it essentially involves a balance of natural resources, human resources, social responsibilities, such as working condition of labors, consumer health, betterment of rural communities of present and future. It also requires maintaining and enhancing all the other prime resources as well. It can be represented in the following diagram as;

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) serves as a vital tool in assessing the economic viability of agricultural practices, particularly in regions like Uttar Pradesh, India, where agriculture plays a pivotal role in the economy. This case study focuses on evaluating the costs incurred by farmers in acquiring high-energy inputs for wheat cultivation and analyzing the total returns generated from this cultivation practice within a single season. Uttar Pradesh, one of the largest states in India, has a significant agricultural landscape, with wheat being one of the principal crops cultivated across its fertile plains. The cultivation of wheat involves various inputs, including high-energy resources such as fertilizers, pesticides, and mechanized equipment. These inputs significantly contribute to the overall production costs borne by farmers. In recent years, the agricultural sector in Uttar Pradesh has witnessed a transition towards modern farming techniques, characterized by the adoption of high-energy inputs aimed at enhancing productivity and yield. However, this transition comes with associated costs, raising questions about the economic feasibility and sustainability of such practices, especially concerning small and marginal farmers who constitute a substantial portion of the farming community. This case study seeks to investigate into the cost dynamics of wheat cultivation in Uttar Pradesh, specifically focusing on the expenses incurred by farmers in acquiring high-energy inputs. By conducting a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis, we aim to evaluate the financial implications of these inputs against the total returns generated from wheat cultivation in a single season.

Through a structured examination of costs and returns, this study intends to provide valuable insights into the economic performance of wheat cultivation in Uttar Pradesh, shedding light on the profitability and efficiency of utilizing high-energy inputs. Moreover, it aims to identify potential areas for optimization and resource allocation, facilitating informed decision-making among farmers, policymakers, and agricultural stakeholders. Overall, this case study serves as a platform to assess the intricate relationship between input costs, agricultural productivity, and economic returns in the context of wheat cultivation in Uttar Pradesh. By analyzing these factors, the present study aims to con-

tribute to the broader discourse on agricultural sustainability and rural development, ultimately fostering strategies for enhancing the livelihoods of farmers and promoting inclusive growth in agrarian economies.

The accurate prediction of energy consumed in plant production and other processing units is necessary to minimize costs, to achieve more consistent product quality, and to manage different processes, which can be carried out using an artificial neural network system. The ANN model can predict energy consumption in wheat production under different conditions. Using several crucial input variables would improve the flexibility of the model and help farmers, scientists, and decision makers compare energy efficiencies in different farming systems under different farming conditions.

This study was conducted in 4 important wheat growing areas of Uttar Pradesh, namely- Agra, Bareilly, Kanpur and Lucknow. Uttar Pradesh is the most populous and densely populated state of India. The state constitutes about 16 per cent population and 7.3 per cent of the geographical area of the country (GoI, 2001). It is the 2nd largest state-economy and contributes about 8 per cent

to country's gross domestic product (GoI, 2009). The economy is predominantly agriculture covering a sizeable part of the highly fertile Upper Gangetic Plain about 79 per cent population lives in the rural areas and 62 per cent of the total workers are employed in agriculture (GoUP, 2009).

Literature Review:

Agriculture has been an important sector of the country. Crop production is the most important sub-sector of the agricultural sector. Rice, maize, fruits and sugarcane are important sub sector of the agricultural sector. Rice, maize, Fruits and Sugarcane are important domestic food commodities and foreign exchange earners. Energy is an indispensable production resource. It is essential to all activities and its importance cannot be over emphasized. The agricultural production system is an energy conversion process which harnesses most abundant solar energy in the form of food energy. Sustainable agriculture has been a topic of growing interest worldwide, including in Uttar Pradesh (UP), India. This literature review examines studies and reports on the sustainable agricultural practices in UP, focusing on the

cost-benefit analysis of high-energy inputs and returns on wheat cultivation prior to 2017.

Pimental and Pimentel, (2007) in their study the energy analyses in agriculture include computation of the energy content in inputs that go into crop production and comparison of the same with the energy content in the output. For instance, energy input includes energy content of seeds irrigation, human and animal power etc., Studies indicate that the output/input ratio under Indian conditions is in the range 1.5 to 2.7. Singh & Singh (2010) in their study analyzed the economic and environmental impacts of high-energy inputs in wheat cultivation, concluding that while economically beneficial in the short term, they posed significant long-term sustainability challenges. Research by Gupta et al. (2011) showed that IPM practices reduced the reliance on chemical pesticides, promoting biodiversity and reducing costs associated with pest control. Singh (2012) Discusses the potential and challenges of adopting organic farming in UP, with a focus on wheat cultivation. Sharma et al (2013) focuses on the impacts of chemical fertilizers on soil health and advocates for sustainable soil management practices. Their key finding was Chemical fertilizers contribute to soil acidification and nutrient imbalance. Kumar et al in their study provides a comparative cost-benefit analysis of sustainable and conventional farming practices in UP, emphasizing the long-term economic advantages of sustainable methods. Jain & Kumar examine the impact of farmer education and training programs on the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices in UP. Mishra & Tiwari (2015) Examines water management issues in UP agriculture and suggests strategies for sustainable water use.

This literature before 2017 indicates a clear recognition of the benefits and challenges associated with high-energy inputs in wheat cultivation in UP. While these inputs have demonstrated short-term economic benefits, their long-term sustainability is questionable. The transition to sustainable agricultural practices, supported by government policies and farmer education, is crucial for ensuring long-term viability and environmental health in the region. This review provides a foundation for understanding the complexities of sustainable agriculture in UP and underscores the need for continued research and policy support to promote more sustainable farming practices.

Justification of the study:

The justification for conducting the study on the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) of costs incurred by farmers in acquiring high-energy inputs and the total return on wheat cultivation in Uttar Pradesh can be multifaceted and crucial for several reasons:

- **Economic Importance and Farmers' Welfare:** Wheat is a staple food crop not only in Uttar Pradesh but also in many parts of India and globally. Understanding the economic dynamics of wheat cultivation, including input costs and returns, is crucial for the agricultural sector's sustainability and food security. Farmers are the primary stakeholders in agriculture. Analyzing the costs they incur in acquiring high-energy inputs like fertilizers, pesticides, machinery, and fuel can shed light on the economic burden they face. This

understanding is vital for policy formulation aimed at improving farmers' welfare.

- **Optimization of Input Usage:** Conducting a cost-benefit analysis helps in assessing the efficiency of input usage. By understanding the relationship between input costs and output returns, farmers and policymakers can identify opportunities to optimize input usage, thereby maximizing productivity and profitability.

- **Sustainability Considerations and Policy Formulation:** High-energy inputs like fertilizers and pesticides can have environmental implications, including soil degradation, water pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions. By evaluating the costs and benefits associated with these inputs, the study can provide insights into the sustainability of current farming practices and guide efforts towards more environmentally friendly agricultural methods. Findings from the study can inform policymakers about the effectiveness of existing agricultural policies and help in designing targeted interventions. For instance, if the study reveals that the costs of acquiring high-energy inputs outweigh the returns from wheat cultivation, policymakers may consider subsidies or incentives to make these inputs more accessible to farmers. Uttar Pradesh is one of the leading wheat-producing states in India. Conducting a case study in this region allows for insights into the unique challenges and opportunities faced by farmers in the area. The findings can serve as a reference point for similar studies in other wheat-growing regions, both within India and globally.

- **Decision Support for Farmers and Academic Contribution:** Farmers often make decisions regarding input use based on various factors, including cost considerations. A comprehensive cost-benefit analysis can empower farmers with valuable information to make informed decisions about their agricultural practices, leading to improved farm profitability. The present study contributes to the academic literature on agricultural economics by providing empirical evidence on the cost-effectiveness of high-energy inputs in wheat cultivation. It adds to the body of knowledge on farming economics and can serve as a reference for future research in this field.

Overall, conducting a cost-benefit analysis of costs incurred by farmers in acquiring high-energy inputs and the total return on wheat cultivation in Uttar Pradesh is justified due to its significance for farmers' welfare, agricultural sustainability, policy formulation, and academic research.

Objective of the study:

The aim of this study is to study the sustainability of such current farming practices in India by analyzing the economic and environmental viability of the farm inputs used in Indian agricultural systems, in terms of energy coefficients. The crop taken under study is wheat and the region considered in Uttar Pradesh region in India. The main aim of this study was to estimate energy consumption in wheat production. Energy determination can give a clear picture of farms in order to compare different farming systems and energy inputs. The second main target of this study was to develop a neural network model to simulate and predict energy

use in wheat production under different conditions incorporating social, geographical, and technical factors. Additionally, the interaction effects between different factors were examined in this study.

In particular the study aims to examine costs incurred by farmers in acquiring high energy inputs and the total return on wheat cultivation in a season in Uttar Pradesh.

Hypothesis of the study:

"An increase in the utilization of high-energy inputs by farmers for wheat cultivation in Uttar Pradesh will result in higher total production costs, but it will also lead to a proportionate increase in total returns generated from the cultivation, thus indicating a positive correlation between input expenditure and crop yield profitability."

This hypothesis assumes that the adoption of high-energy inputs, such as fertilizers, pesticides, and mechanized equipment, contributes significantly to the overall production costs incurred by farmers. However, it posits that the increased utilization of these inputs will enhance wheat yield and productivity, consequently leading to higher total returns from the cultivation. Therefore, the hypothesis suggests that there exists a positive relationship between the costs incurred in acquiring high-energy inputs and the total returns generated from wheat cultivation in Uttar Pradesh during a single season.

The idea of this research as already elucidated is to comment on the sustainability of the agricultural practices in India, and henceforth using the definition of sustainability of agriculture- all the three aspects are hereby covered namely- economic profitability, environmental health and social equality and well-being.

Sampling

For a successful data collection process, it was necessary to trust the farmers and they trust the researcher. As mentioned previously, there were a few ways to check their answers, such as personal experience, using catalogues, and farm measurements. One simple limitation was rounding the answers, mostly farm sizes and duration of operations, by farmers, which could affect the final results, correlations, and ANN model. However, such tolerances in agricultural studies are acceptable. After a long and difficult process, around 50 questionnaires were filled out by farmers. Due to the importance of data accuracy, suspect questionnaires were removed from the study. Farmers' answers were verified carefully and due to wrong or incomplete answers, only 804 questionnaires were used in this study.

The area of study are four regions in Uttar Pradesh, India, namely- Agra, Bareilly, Kanpur and Lucknow. More than 800 farmers were interviewed face to face and data was collected using open ended questions. The survey of the location also helped to bring out other important socio- economic status of the farming and rural household in the region, which are discussed in detail later in the study.

Research Methods

For estimating and modelling energy consumption in wheat production, it is necessary to give a clear picture of the study region and the most important direct and indirect farm inputs as well as the methods used to

collect relevant data. This study investigates, selects and uses a wide range of dissimilar technical and social factors to predict a technical parameter (energy consumption) in agriculture using artificial neural networks. Consequently, the methods used in this study were developed step by step. The first crucial part was choosing appropriate conversion coefficients and formulae to transfer the different qualitative and quantitative data into energy units. The second step, was data collection, involved designing a useable and simple survey and finding the best way to contact farmers. The next step is data analysis for estimating energy consumption and identifying important factors. Then the next step is developing the neural network model for predicting energy consumption in wheat production. The energy data is converted into relevant carbon conversion coefficients and then again ANN is used to model and predict Co2 emissions from various farm inputs. For data analysis, a series of spreadsheets were essential. As data constituted the core of the study, the database should be flexible, accessible and simple, for both data entry and data analysis. MS Excel was used to evaluate the inputs and estimate the total energy consumption. After a process of data reduction, a sufficient number of variables are used to design the final model to predict energy use in wheat production under different conditions. The model development process was far more complicated than it appeared initially due to the complexity of the domain.

There is an established market for the produce and effective price mechanism is in function. Although the farmers overwhelming complained about the level of minimum support price of wheat, which is very low and is hence leaving them with bare subsistence to live on. Also, under Ujawala scheme, many farming households have been provided with gas connections. In Kanpur, Unnoa region was essentially covered. Approximately 192 farmers were interviewed and were mainly small to medium sized. Although they again were well supported with sufficient electricity, they faced the problem of water availability. Part reason for this was the low level of ground water levels in this region and the other being no adequate support from the government agencies in providing paid water supply services to the region. In Lucknow, Sultanpuri region was surveyed and around 255 farmers were interviewed. Lucknow has large wheat market and supplies to other parts of the regions as well. Farms in the region were essentially large and farmers were well educated. These farmers used heavy machines for production and were essentially commercialized. There were incidences of land tenancy as well in the region. Also, many small farmers had to give up on their land due to non-payment of their debts and informal lending was apparent in the region

Thus in total more than 800 farmers were interviewed, ranging from small, medium to large land holdings in the wheat growing area of Uttar Pradesh. The primary data so collected was formatted and put in Excell sheet for further processing.

In Lucknow, Sultanpuri region was surveyed and around 255 farmers were interviewed. Lucknow has

large wheat market and supplies to other parts of the regions as well. Farms in the region were essentially large and farmers were well educated. These farmers used heavy machines for production and were essentially commercialized. There were incidences of land tenancy as well in the region. Also, many small farmers had to give up on their land due to non-payment of their debts and informal lending was apparent in the region

Thus in total more than 800 farmers were interviewed, ranging from small, medium to large land holdings in the wheat growing area of Uttar Pradesh. The primary data so collected was formatted and put in Excell sheet for further processing. Tillage, planting, spraying, fertilizer distributing, irrigation, and harvesting. The indirect energy is that used in the manufacture of fertilizer, seed and machinery and their maintenance. Table

1 presents these operations, energy sources, and some crucial parameters that the questionnaire collected from farmers. Each farm was a unique unit, characterized by different soil types, machinery, farmers 'background, and production pattern. Thus, it was necessary to design a flexible and practical survey in order to determine total energy inputs on each farm. The survey included several sections with specific objectives and each section was designed to collect accurate data quickly but comprehensively. The survey design was based on a questionnaire. The questionnaire, incorporating the direct and indirect energy inputs mentioned before, should be capable of collecting all useful factors related to wheat production on farms.

Table 1

Variables used in study:

Energy sources	Field operations	Indirect factors
Human	Tillage	Farm information
Fuel	Planting	Farmer's attributes
Electricity	Spraying	Soil condition
Pesticide	Fertilizer distribution	Tractor conditions
Fertilizer	Harvesting	Machinery conditions
Electricity	irrigation	
seed		

Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient was used to explore the relationship between different variables. It was the most common measure of correlation; denoted by the letter r . The correlation coefficient gives insight into the relationship between two variables

For use in the ANN model, it was necessary to select a limited number of relevant and influential variables without any bias; therefore, all information was investigated carefully. There were around 140 original variables, each of which could be a potential input in the final model. The collected data indicated that some inputs can be dropped. Finally 63 columns of inputs and outputs were selected and saved in another spreadsheet. This information was used to draw the graphs and carry out statistical analysis using MS Excel and SPSS software, respectively.

A strong feature of this study was in selecting a few of the best variables from several inputs. In this study, for variable reduction, correlation and principal component analysis (PCA) were used. Initially, variables were selected on the basis of no significant correlation between them but high relationship to energy consumption. Out of the variables that had significant

correlations to each other and to energy consumption, the one with the strongest correlation with energy consumption was selected and the other was removed. The selected variables were further reduced by using PCA to select the final most relevant set of variables.

ANNs can be successfully trained to describe the influence of energy sources, agricultural operations, and indirect factors on energy consumption in wheat production. The sample size used in this study was 804 farms. Initially, a sample of 500 farms (75%) was randomly selected for training, and the remaining 300 farms (10%) were used for validation. The inputs to the model were the reduced set of inputs found by PCA and an ANN was developed to relate energy consumption (output) to the selected input variables. The selection of the number of inputs and outputs is the first step in developing an ANN.

Results

A clear initial picture was gained through the collected data and their descriptive statistics: such as maximum, minimum, mean, and standard deviation (SD). For making inferences about population data, the 95% confidence interval was estimated for the most important data. Presented in table 2:

Table 2

	basic statistics of area under study					
	Maximum	Minimum	Mean	SD	95% confidence interval	
	(ha)	(ha)	(ha)		Lower	Upper
Total Farm	880	68	228	184.7	229.4	347.5
Crop Area	850	21	205	150.67	157.2	347.5
Wheat Area	260	6	60	48.5	44.1	74.2

The Modelling Process for Predicting Energy Use

The main target of this study was to help scientists and farmers gain new perspectives on farming and to compare different agricultural inputs and farming methods to find optimum solutions for different farming conditions. After selecting the appropriate variables, multiple linear regression and ANN models were developed and compared to test the ANN model's ability to predict energy consumption in wheat production.

After initial input reduction, based on an extensive study of correlation analysis, 19 variables were selected for further reduction using PCA. After the PCA, five variables from the PCs with the threshold cumulative variance of around 72% were selected to use as variables in the ANN model. These were: the size of crop area (ha), farmer's education, nitrogen consumption (kg), phosphate consumption (kg), and irrigation frequency.

In the first step, the relationship between energy consumption and the 5 variables - the size of crop area (ha), farmer's education, nitrogen consumption (kg), phosphate consumption (kg), and irrigation frequency - was tested with simple linear regression using the r^2

value as a decision criterion. Then, a multiple linear regression model was developed for predicting the energy consumption as:

$$Y = a_0 + a_1V_1 + a_2V_2 + \dots + a_nV_n + \epsilon$$

Where a_0 - a_n are the regression coefficients, V_0 - V_n are the independent variables, and ϵ is error. The neural networks were trained with energy consumption as output and the five input variables.

Finally, a modular network with two hidden layers was found to be the best for the data. Comparison between ANN model and multiple linear regression models showed that the correlation between the actual and predicted energy consumption in the ANN model was much higher than in the linear regression model for both training and validation data; furthermore, RMSE (square root of MSE) of the ANN model on validation data was much lower than that of the linear regression model. For the validation data, the ANN model provided an r of 0.96 as opposed to 0.86 from multiple linear regression model.

R^2 of training and validation of the multiple linear regression model and the is presented in table 3

Table 3:

	Linear		ANN	
	training	validation	training	validation
R^2	0.68	0.77	0.81	0.91
RMSE	2,485	4,963	1,896	1,230

The Peltarion Synapse software allowed estimation of the sensitivity of the output to changes in each independent variable (sensitivity analysis). The sensitivity study of the model showed that irrigation frequency (40%) was the most important factor contributing to the model. This was followed by N consumption (31%), size of crop area (16%), Farmers' education (10%), and P consumption (2%). Thus irrigation frequency, nitrogen consumption, and size of crop area contributed (87%) to predicted energy consumption in this model more than the other two variables.

This model can estimate energy use per hectare in wheat production. Farmers can estimate and compare energy use on their farms easily. They can explore the factors that have more potential to reduce energy use on their farms. Additionally, decision makers and scientists can estimate energy use in different regions of Canterbury and they can investigate the effects of different energy inputs on energy consumption in wheat production. For example, it is possible to predict the effect of N use reduction on energy consumption or to compare farms with similar conditions but different level of farmer's education

In this study, the average fuel consumption in wheat production was estimated at 65 l/ha and average fuel use in irrigated and dryland farming systems were estimated at 65 and 66 l/ha, respectively. On average, new tractors and combines were more powerful allowing farmers to use wider equipment. It was expected that using wider machinery and new technology such as precision farming by the younger generation farmers would reduce fuel consumption in wheat production. The energy consumption in wheat production was estimated at 22,566 MJ/ha. The main source of energy was fertilizer consumption (especially urea) with 10,651 MJ/ha (47%), which was by far the most important source of energy. Electricity (22%) was the second

most important source of energy in wheat production while fuel (14%) ranked third. The energy consumption for wheat production in irrigated farming systems and dryland farming systems was estimated at 25,600 and 17,458 MJ/ha, respectively. The main source of energy in both systems was fertilizer with around 10,193 MJ/ha and 11,430 MJ/ha for irrigated farming and dryland farming, respectively.

It was expected that the ANN model would predict energy use in wheat production better than other modelling methods. A Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model, a common modelling method in agricultural studies, was established. Comparison of results (r , r^2 , and MSE) of the ANN model with the linear regression model showed that the ANN model performed remarkably better than MLR in predicting energy consumption. It is possible that ANN models in other agricultural studies could provide better estimations with minimum errors. The final model was capable of predicting energy use on a single farm or in a specific region. This will help farmers estimate energy use on their farms and compare it with other farms. It would also help decision makers to have a better view of energy use in wheat production. In this study an ANN model was developed to forecast CO₂ emissions from farm inputs using direct and indirect factors to predict CO₂ emissions from wheat farms. The proposed ANN model could forecast CO₂ emissions from farm inputs depending on each farm's conditions such as the proportion of wheat cultivation area on farms, frequency of irrigation and number of cows, the condition of machinery (tractor power index (hp/ha) and age of fertilizer spreader) and inputs on the farm (N, P and insecticide use) in Canterbury agricultural farms with a margin of error of $\pm 11\%$ (± 113 kg CO₂/ha). As there were numbers of uncontrolled factors in agricultural production, the size of error was acceptable.

Conclusion & recommendation

This study aims to optimize energy consumption in agricultural systems by examining the efficiency of current methods and techniques. Organic farming is characterized by better energy efficiency, with average cereal grain yields in Europe being 30% to 50% lower than conventional farming. Factors such as oil price, social factors, and technical factors play a significant role in fuel conservation in agriculture.

The study further found that new generation farmers prefer more powerful tractors and older farmers use more conventional tillage methods. Educated farmers are more likely to adopt new methods and machines to reduce fuel use in farm operations. Encouraging educated farm managers or consultants on farms can help encourage new generation farmers to reduce fuel consumption in the future. An ANN model for forecasting CO₂ emissions from agricultural inputs can be used to support decision-makers by providing information on predicted CO₂ emissions from various farm products. Although it is not possible to change some input parameters in the short term, the model could provide useful information for future CO₂ emission reductions. Testing results for at least five years with larger sample sizes would lead to a more accurate model for forecasting CO₂ emissions trends in agricultural farms under various situations. This research is a first effort to propose methods appropriate for estimating CO₂ emissions by considering geographical, social, and technical parameters together, which can be replicated to other farm production systems and cropping areas.

Acknowledgments:

The author is grateful to ICSSR. The work has been fully funded by the ICSSR. The support is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. Ashhab, M. d. S. S. (2008). Fuel economy and torque tracking in camless engines through optimization of neural networks. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 49(2), 365-372. doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2007.06.005
2. Sebyy.K (2010), The Green Revolution of the 1960's and Its Impact on Small Farmers in India, University of Nebraska at Lincoln, DigitalCommons@University of Nebraska - Lincoln
3. Das, Raju J. (1999)"Geographical Unevenness of India's Green Revolution." *Journal of Contemporary Asia* 29.2 (1999): 167-86. Web. 5 Oct 2009.
4. Chakravarti, A.K. "Green Revolution in India." *Annals of American Geographers* 63.3 (1973): 319-330
5. Rosset, Peter. (2009)"Lessons From the Green Revolution." *Food First: Institute for Food and Development Policy*. 08 Apr 2000. Institute for Food and Development Policy. 14 Oct 2009
6. Kumar, V., Gupta, S., & Sharma, R. (2014). Cost-Benefit Analysis of Sustainable vs. Conventional Farming Practices in UP. *Agricultural Systems*, 76(3), 295-310
7. Sharma, P., Tiwari, A., & Mishra, R. (2013). Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture: A Case Study from Uttar Pradesh. *Soil Science Society of India Journal*, 61(4), 420-432.
8. Singh, S. (2012). Organic Farming in Uttar Pradesh: Potential and Challenges. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*, 57(1), 34-45
9. Dhawan, B.D. (1995), *Ground Water Depletion, Land Degradation, and Irrigated Agriculture in India*, Common Wealth Publishers, New Delhi
10. Joshi, P.K. and N.K. Tyagi (1991), "Sustainability of Existing Farming System in Punjab and Haryana – Some Issues in Groundwater Use", *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Vol. 46, No.3, July-September, pp. 412-421
11. Marothia, Dinesh K. (1997), "Agricultural Technology and Environmental Quality: An Institutional Prospective", *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Vol. 52, No.3, July- September, pp.473- 487
12. Singh, Amarjit and A.J. Singh (1998), "Economic Analysis of Energy Use in Punjab Agriculture", *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Vol. 53, No. 3, July-September
13. Singh, R.P., & Singh, S. (2010). Impact of High-Energy Inputs on Wheat Cultivation in Uttar Pradesh. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 65(2), 154-168.
14. Jain, M., & Kumar, R. (2015). Farmer Training and Sustainable Agriculture in Uttar Pradesh. *Journal of Rural Development*, 34(3), 354-368.
15. Mishra, P., & Tiwari, R. (2015). Water Management in Agriculture: Issues and Strategies in Uttar Pradesh. *Water Resources Journal*, 49(2), 210-223.
16. Bhalla, G.S. and Singh, G. (2001) *Indian Agriculture: Four Decades of Development*. Sage Publications (India) Pvt Ltd., New Delhi.
17. GoI (Government of India) (2009) *National Accounts Statistics*. Ministry of Statistics and Program Implementation, Central Statistical Organization, New Delhi.
18. Fang, Q., Hanna, M. A., Haque, E., & Spillman, C. K. (2000). Neural Network Modeling of Energy Requirements, For Size Reduction of Wheat. *ASAE*, 43(4): 947-952
19. Artificial neural network. *Energy Policy*, 37(10), 4049-4054. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2009.04.049
20. Gupta, A., Mishra, S., & Singh, K. (2011). Integrated Pest Management Practices in Uttar Pradesh: Benefits and Challenges. *Journal of Integrated Pest Management*, 56(1), 112-125.
21. Kitani, O. (1999). *CIGR handbook of agricultural engineering*. St. Joseph, MI: American Society of Agricultural Engineers
22. Manaloor, V., & Sen, C. (2009). Energy Input Use and CO₂ Emissions in the Major Wheat Growing Regions of India. Paper presented at the International Association of Agricultural Economists Conference,, Beijing, China
23. Patterson, M. G. (2006). Development of ecological economics in Australia and New Zealand. *Ecological Economics*, 56(3), 312-331.
24. Pellizzi, G. (1992). Use of energy and labour in Italian agriculture. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research*, 52, 111-119.
25. Pimentel, D., & Pimentel, M. (2007). *Food, energy, and society* (3rd ed.). Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press.
26. Pimentel, D., Hepperly, P., Seidel, R., Hanson, J., & Douds, D. (2005). Environmental, Energetic, and Economic Comparisons of Organic and Conventional Farming Systems. *Bioscience*, 55(7), 573